
OCCUPATIONAL STRESS AMONG TEACHERS –A LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract: Any type of change that causes physical, emotional or psychological strain it results in stress. Every one experiences some kind of stress in their day to day life. Stress for teachers in a growing concern is due to fearness of safety of job, long working hours, and low morale. These factors contributing to work place stress has proved to stand as a detrimental effect on health of the teachers, which in turn affects the students and as well as learning environment. The aim of the study is to critical review of existing literature available on occupational stress level of teachers. The study also focuses on strategies adopted by the teachers to cope with occupational stress and concluding with finding out the research gap with regarding to stress level among college teachers.

Keywords: Teachers, learning environment, occupational stress, coping strategies.

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Introduction

Education is the process of instruction aimed to develop the knowledge, attitude and character of individuals for preparing them to live in a meaningful way. The teacher forms the most important link in our educational system. Success of any educational programme depends largely upon the efficiency level of the teachers. A person, who inspires, encourages strive for greatness is the role model of our life and that could be any one but the person who guides us in the right direction is the teacher. Stress not only affects the physical and psychological state but also had an adverse impact on family and social life of employees [1] Stress is not always negative. It results in eustress and distress. Eustress helps in restoring our energy and distress normally has a negative impact on our performance [2]. The work related stress emerges due to a pattern of emotional, cognitive, behavioural and physiological reactions to adverse and noxious aspects of work content, work organization and work environment [3]. Each profession has its own work related stress. Teaching as a profession is no more the profession of a little stress [4]. Teacher's experiences stress due to hazardous working conditions, a lack of

materials and lack of output from the administration [5]. Teachers stress is a reaction of teachers to the unwanted environment factors. The stress level of teachers negatively affects the performance level of the teachers by lowering their productivity as well as it affects the performance level of the educational institution [6]. Majority of teachers perceived their work related stress due to dependent variables like gender, education, family income and economic instability [7]. Job insecurity, poor students behaviour, ineffective leadership at departmental levels results in stress level of teachers and it also results in psychological distress among teachers. [8]. Educational status and years of experience of teachers are the factors responsible for creating stress among teachers [9].

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to assess the level of occupational stress and coping strategies of the teachers working in universities, secondary schools, elementary schools and colleges; by making an exhaustive literature review.

Research methodology:

The present study tried to find out some of the research works done in the area taking into account the objectives of the study. Only secondary sources of data considered for the study. Secondary data consists of articles, journals, and website, magazine and conference proceedings.

Purpose of the study:

The purpose of this study is to gain an knowledge of concepts of stress, stressors and coping strategies in order to reduce stress level of teachers.

Factors causing occupational stress

Occupational stress is an unavoidable phenomenon in human life. Occupational stress affects an individual's productivity, effectiveness, personal health and quality of work. Identification of factors causing stress among the teacher educators at work place is very necessary [10]. Personal and social characteristics and working conditions may have an effect on teachers stress level [11]. Under different dimensions of occupational stress the upper primary school teachers differed significantly with various variables like teaching experience, workload and it is treated as one of the maximum stressor causes stress among teachers [12]. Secondary school teachers perceived more stress in all stress factors which are rapport with parent, rapport with the co- worker, workload and lack of resources [13]. An empirical analysis among teachers working in higher education sector

in Kerala explores the nine factors ,which significantly influence the organizational stress they are interpersonal relationship in the organisation, professional and competence development, recognition in the organisation, work environment, autonomy in work, work family interaction, role conflict, job security and remuneration and non-academic[14]. The teachers have many activities to carry out in the process of executing their main duty of teaching. It is considered as one of the factor responsible for assessing risk level of teachers. Other than this other variables like resources, communication level and interpersonal relationship of the teachers in working area are also the factors responsible for assessing stress level of teachers[15].The teachers working in state government, public, missionary, army and navodayalas of Kashmir valley , study reveals that age, qualification and ,marital status are affecting occupational stress of teachers.[16].The study conducted in Bribhum District of West Bengal identifies that demographic factors influence the stress level of teachers. The study opined that teachers working in the self-financing institutions are more stressful than teachers working in government institution. The study revealed that self role distance, work overload, role of ambiguity, role of conflict are the stressful factors among stressful and stress less teachers. [17]. The relevant information from secondary government schools of Mandi District of Himachal Pradesh identifies that teachers facing high, moderate and low level of occupational stress in their work[18].Asamankese Circuit 11 in West Akim Municipality of Ghana reveals that female teachers more stressed due to workload and interpersonal relationship and it made them perform below standard [19]. The most important factor that creates stress is Salary and other benefits followed by working conditions, relations with colleagues, job security and work load. So by improving these factors job stress can be reduces among college teachers [20] .The study reveals that the female teachers have reported that they have faced the problems of occupational stress in performing their duties like heavy workload, family interference, in adequate salary and student behaviour [21].The study made in Secondary schools in Esan Central Senatorial District, Edo, State Nigeria observed that the teachers faces risk due to work overload, crowded class conditions, poor working conditions, lack of social support and lack of accessories. Stress lessens teachers' quality of instructional delivery, lowers teacher's morale, job satisfaction, job performance and increases attrition [22]. The study opined that the stress associated to student's disruptive behaviour and to difficulties perceived by teachers in managing conflicts has a greater incidence of female teachers, on second cycle teachers and on intermediate stages in the profession[23].The study investigates about the highest levels of perceived teacher's work related stress were caused by changes in terms and conditions, without consultation given responsibility, without the authority to take decisions; while in the category support, the same was true for stress factors lack of funds of resources to do the job and limited or no access to training[24].After reviewing the different studies, the researcher found few similarities in factors responsible for occupational stress in teaching

environment i.e. working environment, age factor and job security besides that paid leave role conflict and technological changes are the factors, which lead to occupational stress in international scenario[25].The study reveals that the factors seen concrete satisfaction for male teachers of the government sector are profile and work role flexibility, security of job, high wage and freedom in the autonomy or decision making in the job profile. This looks the opposite in the case of private school teachers as factors such as salary, decision making seems to be dissatisfied for the teachers [26]. It is found that all the selected female teachers have reported that they have faced the problem of occupational stress in performing their duties due to different reasons. Large class size, lack of opportunities for professional management, students behaviour, inadequate salary, lack of healthy interaction among staffs and shortage of time to cover the syllabus, lack of proper teaching aids, heavy workload, financial problem at home, family interference into their career [27].The study results showed part time/full time status, age, job satisfaction and negative religious coping as significant predictors of faculty stress. Significant negative correlations between job satisfaction, reward and recognition, departmental influence are factors causing stress among teachers [28].The study found that stress levels are affected by numerous factors in educational institutions. Poor relations with workmates, lack of regular breaks, long working hours, harassment by staff, lack of communication, poor pay prospects, pace and intensity of change and limited access to training [29]. It can be concluded that insufficient remuneration is the major factor influencing stress at the work place among the contractual teachers, followed by work life conflict, personal factors, job insecurity, classroom related factors, interpersonal relations and workload. It is also clear from the study that most of the teachers are given service break every semester, resulting in job insecurity among them and thereby resulting in increase in employees' turnover and decrease in the efficiency level of the employees [30]

Stress management

Stress management is named as one of the keys to a happy and successful life in modern society. Although life provides numerous demands that can prove difficult to handle, stress management provides a number of ways to manage anxiety and maintain overall wellbeing. Stress management is a wide spectrum of techniques and psychotherapies aimed at controlling a person's level of stress. The study reveals that excessive additional duty, involvement in non-teaching duty, negative attitude of colleagues, lack of motivation, lack of research and personal growth, work from home are the factors affecting stress level among teachers. In times of great stress, it's always best to keep busy, to plow anger and energy into something positive. Positive attitude and Meditation will be helpful for copying the stress [31]. Stress mainly occurs when the pressure is greater than the resource. We create most of our own aspects in our daily life through our way of responding things in a negative way

which may be due to lack of awareness inability to perceive things as they are ought to be. [32]. The study investigates about various factors stimulating stress level among college teachers in Andhra Pradesh. Workplace stress occurs when there is an imbalance in the demands and perceived pressure of the work environment and a specific ability to cope [33]. The study conducted in Nigeria it explores that average Nigerian teacher prefers to organize him/ herself in such a way that his/her pedagogic duties will not be hampered by domestic chores. Majority of teachers never engage in physical exercises, watch films in order to manage any stressful situations, they prefer to keep away from any situation that could cause stress, as well as endeavouring to separate themselves from people who causes stressful situations [34]. The study opined that major causes of teacher stress categorised into academic, administrative, government policies, personal problems and time management [35]. The study conducted in Melbourne indicates that student misbehaviours are a common concern for teachers. The use of predominantly relative management strategies has a significant relationship with elevated teacher stress. In order to combat their stress and perform their duties for longevity in the classroom teachers cannot be expected to resolve all the issues of their jobs on their own, support from colleagues and administrators important [36]. The study opined that working conditions, living conditions and lack of resources were the main sources of stressors, while physical exercises, religious intervention, use of alcohol were coping strategies used [37]. Stress happens whenever one's mind and body reacts to some real or probable situation. The study reveals that the level of stress is more due to the increase in population, long working hours, lack of time, torture by seniors etc. [38]. The study reveals that majority of teachers are experiencing work stress due to nature of job, role stress, personal development stress, interpersonal relationship and organizational climate. The study also suggested best coping strategies in order to overcome up with stress [39]. The study observed that heavy workload, much pressure to take up the result; efforts of teachers not recognized by institution are major factors influencing stress level among teachers. The study also suggested stress coping strategies in order to reduce the stress level of teachers; concentrating and giving more importance to finance problems, organizational changes to be properly communicated, doing activities in order to feel relaxed like taking a brisk walk, stretching etc. [40]. Stress at the work place is the major cause of most of the health problems. The study opined that college teachers are stressed more due to external factors and through the poor student behaviour and results. In order to manage the stress the teachers adopted coping strategies like sharing stress problems with friends and reading books. [41]. The study reveals that 'escape avoidance, accepting responsibility and uncontrolled aggression' were used as negative coping strategies and only one strategy, 'exercise' was indicated to be an effective way of coping [42]. There was no significant difference between special education and general class room teachers in relation to all sources and effects of stress. The study showed that most sources of stress had a weak- positive correlation

with the coping strategies; yet most effects of stress had a weak – negative correlation with coping strategies [43]. The study explores that the teachers experienced high levels of emotional exhaustion and personal accomplishment and used self-confident, searching social support and optimistic coping strategies in coping stressful situations. The study also indicates that the self-confident coping strategy was the significant predictor of personal accomplishment and negative correlation with personal accomplishment. [44] Results also revealed insignificant differences for coping strategies in relation to gender and subject streams but significant differences for nature of job. The linear regression model showed a significant negative relationship between occupational stress and coping strategies [45]. The study observed that cent percent of the respondents were sometimes irritated during the teaching hours due to the work pressure and due to the extra burden given by authorities. Majority of respondents agreed that one could manage stress by creating a good balance between work and family and from co-workers support network [46].The study opined that in professional stressors category the stress factor of new teaching methods, in economic stressors category the stress factor of job insecurity, in student stressors category the stress factor of violence and aggression, in social and professional stressors category the stress factor of lack of public esteem and the college as a stressful workplace category the stress factor of lack of control and autonomy are having more mean score when compared to other stresses[47].The study exhibits that the most important causes for stress among faculties are overloaded working hours, role in the performance of job, student discipline, innovations in the higher education field, career development, funding policies, problems arise from administration side, feeling of angry, whipping by finished tiredness and unfit to move in work are considered as the essential results of stress among the teachers[48].The study opined that relationship of the respondents profile has no direct influence on teaching effectiveness, while the relationship of occupational stress and teaching effectiveness, found a slight negative relationship; it results in decreasing performance level of teachers. They also inferred that the respondents performance was not affected by the occupational stress but evidently on effectiveness by dedication and commitment of teachers to their profession [49]. The need for knowledge for personal growth and national development puts pressure on the teachers to facilitate the achievement of these goals. The study opined that working conditions, living conditions and lack of resources were the main sources of stressors, while physical exercises and religious intervention treated as stress coping strategies used by teachers in order to reduce their stress level [50].

Research Gap and conclusion:

After reviewing the literature available on level of stress among teachers' it is found that few similar factors were responsible for level of stress in teaching environment i.e. work load, job insecurity etc. The study also

observed about coping strategies adopted by the teachers in order to reduce their stress level. However, the fact of the matter remains, stress cannot be eliminated from the organisations completely. But stress can only be reduced with the help of workplace as well as personal interventions to optimum level. As per the study it is observed that teachers facing different levels of stress in their working life but what kind of stress level faced by teachers particularly women teachers in degree colleges was not particularly analysed. So, the further research based on ‘ ‘ Stress management among women employees of degree colleges’ ’; in order to identify different levels of stress faced by government and private college teachers in their working environment and as well as in order to know copying strategies.

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